

KENYA'S CLEWS MODEL WORKING PAPER A CLEWS MODEL FOR KENYA

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Introduction

The Republic of Kenya is an East African country with an area of around 224x10³ km². Even though the country has faced growth due to investments in infrastructure such as road, rail, and water transport, the country is at a lower rank among fragile states [1].

Investments in electrification have enabled approximately 71% of the population to have access to electricity in the country; however, access to electricity is lower compared to other countries [2]. Rural electrification is still lower at 62% compared to urban areas, where it reaches 94%.

In 2020, the Republic of Kenya had a total installed electricity supply capacity of around 3 GW. Most of the capacity is central generating stations under the Kenya Electricity Generating Company (KenGen). Conventional generators comprise only 24% of the capacity (720 MW). At the same time, renewables, including bioenergy, hydropower, solar, wind, and geothermal power plants, account for 76%. Fossil fuels are used for industrial and transport purposes. However, only 20% of the population has access to clean cooking fuels, as wood and charcoal are still the primary energy sources in urban and rural areas [2].

The Republic of Kenya aims to reduce its reliance on fossil fuels for industry and transport, decrease biomass use in the cooking sector, improve energy security, and reduce emissions. The country's plans include interventions in all sectors, including power, to provide clean, sustainable, and affordable energy services [3,4].

Since interventions include the electricity and other sectors, it is essential to develop models that help assess broader sector interactions with energy and transport systems and climate-resilient system choices and their linkages. The existing Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Strategies (CLEWs) model framework is a well-established foundation to explore these sector interdependencies. This frame allows analysts and modelers to consider other sectors and resource interdependencies. Examples of how the CLEWs framework has been used in several study cases and the implementation from key concepts to model implementation are presented by Ramos et al. [5,6].

This study emphasizes using existing open-source energy models developed for Kenya. The first model, created by UCL as part of WS3, includes the whole energy system and sectors such as the power, industrial, and transport sectors, among others. The second model is a CLEWs model tailored for the country. This model focuses on interlinkages between the energy and land systems. Interlinkages are exemplified or represented in the cooking sector (energy) and the agricultural sector (land). Both models encompass energy systems; however, the CLEWs model brings in other resource systems, such as land and water.

Merging both models has the potential to capture interactions between systems; for example, fossil fuels are used not only in the energy system for electricity generation but also in the land and water systems for mechanization and pumping, respectively. Similarly, electricity is used also for irrigation and public water distribution.

Both models have individual data input parameters, and although similar units were used, the data carries uncertainties. As such, another future step after merging both models is to carry out a global sensitivity analysis (GSA) [7]. A GSA allows the identification of influential and non-influential parameters in the model. Influential parameters can produce a significant change in model results, in other words, in the objective function. The objective (OF) function is the key to ESM's optimization problem (LP). In this case, the OF seeks to minimize the total system cost associated with energy supply, distribution, and consumption. It includes infrastructure (power plant cost), operation, maintenance, and fuel costs.

Identifying influential input parameters is part of factor prioritization, which helps to understand model behavior and contributes to the scientific discussion on sectoral interactions within energy system models (ESM). The expected findings will have implications in the integrated land, energy, and water systems and provide valuable insights into the importance of specific parameters in the CLEWs modeling framework.

1. Materials and Methods

Background

The WESM (Kenya Whole Energy System Model) is an energy system model developed in OSeMOSYS. The WESM has a detailed description of the power sector [8] and all other significant sectors that contribute to energy consumption in Kenya, such as agriculture, industry, transport, and the commercial and residential sectors, as shown in Figure 1. Data, assumptions, and derived demands can be accessed in [9–11].

Figure 1. Kenya Whole Energy System Model (WESM). Adapted from [9]

The CLEWs model presents a long-term model for Kenya that integrates climate, land, energy, and water systems under one modeling framework. This model is also developed in OSeMOSYS. The integration is focused on energy and land systems in Kenya, particularly emphasizing the cooking and agricultural sectors (see Figure 2). The cooking sector uses several stoves that can meet cooking service demand, driven by the energy needed to cook a meal [12]. The agricultural sector encompasses seven crops, i.e., wheat, beans, maize, tea, coffee, sugarcane, and barley, representing around 72% of the crop area in the country. Both cooking and agricultural sectors are represented in the model for being responsible for reductions in forest cover areas. Additional data and information on the model can be accessed in [13].

Figure 2. Kenya CLEWs model. Adapted from [13]

Objectives of the Working Paper:

This Working Paper aims to describe how the WESM and CLEWs models have been integrated.

The integration of the WESM and CLEWs model for Kenya has the following objectives:

- To identify common elements shared between both models.
- In energy systems and optimization models, these elements are called parameters. Parameters are numerical inputs in the model, which simultaneously are a function of the sets. Sets are the physical structure of both models. Sets define time and spatial coverage as the most essential factors in merging both models and the common technologies and energy vectors in both models.
- To create the whole CLEWs model for Kenya, including data and advances from WS3 and WS4-CLEWs.
- To establish additional cross-sectoral linkages between the energy sector in the WESM and the energy, land, and water systems in the CLEWs model.
- The emphasis of linkages is on the cooking sector, land use, and fuel consumption across systems.
- To identify the most influential input parameters that have a relative effect on the CLEWs model for Kenya.

2. Methodology

A systematic approach was used to merge the WESM and CLEWs Kenya model. Figure 3 provides an overview of the process involved in merging both models. Initially, the input data from both models should be open, accessible, and have a similar format. Data input files have all the input parameters included in both models. The initial format in both data input files is presented as text files (*.txt). However, both text files can be easily converted to a more computer-friendly format, *.csv format. With *.csv format, it is easy to handle data, and therefore, it is straightforward to read and write data. Such a format also benefits from being independent of the operating system and programming language. Converting from *.txt to *.csv format is also straightforward; the Python package OTOOLE was used in this case. Examples of data conversion and other library functionalities can be found in the documentation [14]. When both input data files from both

models are in CSV format, it is possible to merge them. A simplified version of merging is explained in Section 0. A Python script performs the merging operation and plots the new merged model as CSV files; in this operation, the configuration file (`config.yaml`) is also an input. Then, it is possible to have the merged model as a `.txt` file again, create an LP file, and solve the LP file using free-open solvers such as GLPK, CBC, or commercial and also accessible through educational institutions such as CPLEX and GUROBI. Finally, the library `otoole` converts the solution file (`*.SOL`), an output from solving an LP file, to a more friendly format such as CSV or XLS format.

A workflow using the Python library Snakemake summarizes merging both models. The workflow and data are accessible through the GitHub repository and cataloged in [15].

Figure 3. Merging WESM-CLEWs workflow

Merging WESM/CLEWs

The units in both models are similar; for example, technology costs are given in millions of dollars per gigawatt (MM/GW). Fuel costs are given in millions of dollars per petajoule (MM/PJ). Once both models are in `*.CSV` format, the Python script/workflow attached is used to:

- Read the common technologies (tech) and fuels. Table 1 shows the common tech and fuel found in both models.
- Update the technology and fuel names in the CLEWs model. For instance, change the fuel name 'ELC' in the CLEWs model to 'ELC003,' which is the electricity provided after transmission and distribution in the WESM.
- Delete repeated common technologies like those highlighted in grey in Table 1 in the CLEWs model.
- Update the Region name from the CLEWs model ('RE1') to the name in the WESM ('KENYA').
- Update the units of emission activity ratio in the merged model to kilotons of CO_2 per petajoule ($kTon/PJ$)
- Remove common techs from the CLEWs model. This also applies to removing repeated technologies in the Sets: TECHNOLOGY and FUEL.
- Merge the two models
- Save the merged model as `*.csv` format.
- To print the files, the configuration file `*.YAML` file must be configured. The configuration file also uses 'otoole convert' commands to print results.

Table 1. Common tech and fuels across both models.

	WESM				CLEWs			
	KENYA	KENYA	KENYA	KENYA	RE1	RE1	RE1	RE1
REGION	IMPDSL	IMPELC	IMPKER	IMPLPG	IMPDSL	IMPELC	IMPKER	IMPLPG
TECHNOLOGY	DSL	ELC003	KER	LPG	DSL	ELC	KER	LPG
FUEL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
MODE_OF_OPERATION	2019	2019	2019	2019	2019	2019	2019	2019
YEAR								

Merging both models also helps to identify additional interlinkages since it is rather difficult to distinguish interlinkages between systems when having two separate models. The linkages include those for public water and additional water use, for example, in the residential and commercial sectors. In addition, water is used in one way or another for electricity generation, for example, for cooling thermal power plants, and water is used in hydropower and geothermal plants. Extending the study and adding additional water use are possible regarding geothermal energy. However, this depends on data availability for this specific sector. For example, geothermal power plants use water as a working fluid injected into the earth's crust, and then hot water or steam is used to drive turbines. Water is also used for cooling purposes and usually is recycled. Yet, water used in geothermal energy can be considered in a water balance if the study is likely to consider water scarcity or competing water demands. This highlights the importance of efficient water management practices, such as water recycling, thus minimizing water losses. Water use is important since Kenya has an installed capacity and significant geothermal potential. Table 2 presents additional linkages and open data that can be used to represent the use of different commodities/fuels and technologies. Column System A refers to the initial system in which the resource is taken; for example, water is a resource or a commodity that is taken or withdrawn to be used in cooling power plants, public, and irrigation. System B is the system where the fuel/or commodity is used; for instance, water is used in the energy system for cooling power plants and in the land system to irrigate crops.

Table 2. Additional linkages between systems

System A	Linkage A-B	System B	Reference
<i>Water</i>	Water is used to cool thermal power plants. Including coal and diesel/hfo/lfo power plants	<i>Power Sector</i>	Coal [16], Table 4 Addition thermal technologies [17], Figure 1
<i>Water</i>	Water for hydropower		
<i>Water</i>	Water for geothermal	<i>Power Sector</i>	Water consumption in geothermal [17], Figure 2
<i>Water</i>	Water abstraction, surface water, and groundwater.	<i>Water</i>	Section: Water Abstracted under Permit [18–20].

Integration Challenges

While merging the models, some integration challenges exist, such as data gaps and model-specific equations. Regarding data gaps, even though both models have repositories of open data that are accessible to download, only the CLEWs model discusses challenges in gathering data to populate such a nexus model. In addition, the CLEWs models present specific uncertain parameters by showing the ranges of values for different input parameters. Additional interlinkages like those presented in **Table 2** will need more data to represent the linkages between systems. Another integration challenge is the use of different models. The model file in the modeling framework OSeMOSYS contains the mathematical representation, including all the sets, parameters, equations, and constraints necessary to represent the analyzed energy systems. However, the

model files found for both the WES and CLEWs models are different. While the CLEWs model contains a specific equation used to represent land use, the WESM does not have it. Similarly, the WESM model file does not include the latest equations to represent the individual discount rates that generation technologies can have [21]. Individual discount rates can be used to adjust for differences in the perceived risk of investment in a technology. Therefore, an updated model file was developed based on the latest release of OsEMOSYS from the GitHub repository [22]. This model file contains all the necessary equations to build an LP file from the merged data file.

3. Expected results

The expected results from the development of the merged CLEWs model for Kenya include:

- Kenya CLEWs Model

Developing an open-source CLEWs model tailored to Kenya's specific context is also aligned with the u4RIA goals [23]. This model can help stakeholders assess the interlinkages between climate, land, energy, and water systems and facilitate the development of integrated and sustainable policies encompassing several sectors related to policy coherence. Similarly to the
- The energy mix from 2019 to 2050 from a cost optimization perspective:

Results involve the energy mix for Kenya from 2019 to 2050, considering several factors such as technological advancements, resource availability, policy changes, and demand projections. Additionally, the model can consider the use of land and water resources and production per crop area.
- The effect of adding sectoral interaction, climate, land, energy, and water on the overall results is factor prioritization because of performing a GSA.

A Global Sensitivity Analysis (GSA) will help identify which input parameters used to represent the sectors have the most significant influence on the overall results of the model. Results include factor prioritization based on their impact on the model outcomes, which could highlight areas where policy interventions or further research may be needed. By understanding the model's sensitivity to several factors, decision-makers can focus on addressing the most influential variables to improve the robustness and effectiveness of energy policies and strategies in Kenya.

4. The value of the research; benefits

This working paper presents the creation of a Climate, Land, Energy & Water model for Kenya that includes the whole energy system, merging a WESM and a previous CLEWs application. The model focuses on transitioning from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources in the long term. The open-source model enables transfer to various stakeholders for further research and improvement. An open-source energy system model generator allows for substantial cost savings in software expenses. Additionally, the open-source nature of the model invites active participation from multiple stakeholders in modeling and implementing future energy policies through capacity building. As a result, this research is expected to significantly contribute to the development of future energy policies, investment analysis, resource management/allocation, and the illustration of Kenya's transition towards renewables and its impact on various sectors. Aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), this study primarily supports Goal #7: Affordable and Clean Energy. However, integrating additional systems such as climate, water, and land in the model is beneficial since it could expand the alignment to other SDGs, such as Goal#2: Zero hunger.

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